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Perspectives on child labor in the Arab World and Lebanon!

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, the Arab World has seen a large wave of armed conflicts and population displacement, which is thought to have resulted in an increase in child labor, the magnitude of which is still unknown. Armed conflicts have exacerbated pre-existing levels of child labor in rural and urban areas, which are typically driven by economic vulnerability, poor education, and certain social norms. Children, society's most vulnerable members, have been especially hard hit. They are increasingly drawn into the most heinous forms of child labor, where they face serious and concerning exploitation, abuse, and violations of their rights. These forms include hazardous work in agriculture, services, industry, as well as street work. Further, the Arab region has seen an alarming increase in the use of children in illicit activities, such as prostitution and armed conflicts, often under forced or bonded-labor conditions. The aim of this paper is to address child labor in the Arab World in general, and in Lebanon in particular.

1. INTRODUCTION

Globally, governments and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) are concerned about the prevalence of child labor. People all over the world are looking for the quickest and most thorough ways to protect children from the negative impact of child labor on their physical, mental, and emotional development.

1.1 What exactly is meant by the term "child labor"?

Child labor is defined by the International Labour Organization (ILO) as work that is mentally, physically, socially, or morally hazardous to children and interferes with their education by:

- depriving them of the opportunity to attend school;
- obliging them to leave school prematurely; or
- requiring them to combine school attendance with excessively long and heavy work.

The child's age, the nature of the activity, the number of hours spent on it, the working conditions, and the goals of each country all play a role in determining whether a particular type of "work" constitutes

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"child labor." The response differs from country to country, and even within a country, from industry to industry.

While it is critical to eliminate as much child labor as possible, this does not apply to all child labor. Most people believe that it is beneficial for children and teenagers who are legally allowed to work to do so in jobs that do not jeopardize their health or development, or interfere with their education. This includes helping out at the family business after school and on weekends, as well as doing extra work over the summer. Children and their families benefit from these kinds of events because they teach children important lessons about life, help them learn important skills, and prepare them for success as adults.

1.2 Inhumane methods of child labor

Some of the worst kinds of child labor are slavery, separating children from their families, putting children in danger, and leaving children alone on the streets of large cities.

While there are many different types of child labor, the worst forms, as defined in Article 3 of the International Labor Organization's (ILO) Convention No. 182, must be eliminated:

- all forms of slavery or practices similar to slavery, such as the sale and trafficking of children, debt bondage and serfdom and forced or compulsory labour, including forced or compulsory recruitment of children for use in armed conflict;
- the use, procuring, or offering of a child for prostitution, for the production of pornography, or for pornographic performances;
- the use, procuring, or offering of a child for illicit activities, in particular for the production and trafficking of drugs, as defined in the relevant international treaties;
- work that, by its nature or the circumstances in which it is carried out, is likely to harm the health, safety, or morals of children.

1.3 The perils of child labor

According to the ILO and the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP):

- 152 million children worldwide are victims of child labor; 88 million are boys and 64 million are girls (ILO, 2017).
- Girls are more likely than boys to shoulder responsibility for household chores, a type of work not considered in child labor estimates (ILO, 2017).
- Girls are more likely than boys to drop out of school early to take care of chores at home. Boys, on the other hand, are more likely to drop out of school early to go to work (ILO, 2017).
- Children aged 5 to 11 make up 48% of all child labor victims (ILO, 2017).
- Nearly half of the people who work as child laborers (73 million) do dangerous work, and children under 12 do more than a quarter of the dangerous work (19 million) (ILO, 2017).
- 71 percent of child labor takes place in agriculture, which includes fishing, forestry, livestock herding, and aquaculture (ILO, 2017).
- 19 percent of child labor victims live in low-income countries; 2 million victims live in high-income countries (ILO, 2017).

- There is a strong correlation between child labor and situations of conflict and disaster. The incidence of child labor in countries affected by armed conflict is 77 percent higher than the global average; the incidence of hazardous work is 50 percent higher (ILO, 2017).
- The illegal profits from forced labor are thought to be around \$150 billion a year (UNDP, 2015).
- More than two-thirds of all children in child labor (69.1 percent) work as laborers on family farms and in family businesses (ILO, 2017).
- Children who have to leave school before they turn 15 because of problems at home or other things are less likely to ever get a job (ILO, 2015).
- Former child laborers are much more likely to have only a primary education or less (ILO, 2015).
- Young people who work as child laborers (up to the age of 15) are more likely to be in low-paying jobs (ILO, 2015).
- Almost half of child laborers are in Africa (72.1 million), and 41 percent (62.1 million) are in Asia and the Pacific (ILO, 2017).

1.4 ILO Conventions on child labor

The two ILO Conventions on Child Labor are Convention No. 138 on the Minimum Age and Convention No. 182 on the Worst Forms of Child Labor. These Conventions are "fundamental" Conventions. This means that, under the ILO Declaration on Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work, all ILO member states have an obligation to respect, promote, and realize the abolition of child labor, even if they have not ratified the Conventions in question.

These conventions and recommendations are alluded to in the following: (ILO Conventions on child labor, n.d.):

ILO Minimum Age Convention, 1973 (No. 138) and its Recommendation No. 146

One of the most effective methods of ensuring that children do not start working too young is to set the age at which children can legally be employed or otherwise work. The aim of ILO Convention No. 138 on the minimum age is the effective abolition of child labor by requiring countries to establish a minimum age for entry into work or employment, and establish national policies for the elimination of child labor.

Recommendation No. 146

The Recommendation No. 146, which accompanies Convention No. 138, stresses that national policies and plans should provide for: poverty alleviation and the promotion of decent jobs for adults, so that parents do not need to resort to child labor; free and compulsory education and the provision of vocational training; the extension of social security and systems for birth registration; and appropriate facilities for the protection of children and adolescents who work. To achieve the elimination of child labor, laws setting the minimum age for work should be embedded in such comprehensive policy responses.

ILO Worst Forms of Child Labor Convention, 1999 (No. 182) and its Recommendation No. 190

Child labor, as the statistics clearly demonstrate, is a problem of immense global proportions. Following its comprehensive research into the issue, the ILO concluded that it was necessary to strengthen existing conventions on child labor. Convention No. 182 helped to focus the international spotlight on the urgency of action to eliminate, as a priority, the worst forms of child labor without losing sight of the long-term goal of the effective elimination of all child labor. Convention No. 182 requires countries to take immediate, effective, and time-bound measures to eliminate the worst forms of child labor.

Recommendation No. 190

The Recommendation No. 190, which accompanies Convention No. 182, recommends that any definition of "hazardous work" include: work that exposes children to physical, psychological, or sexual abuse; work underground, underwater, at dangerous heights, or in confined spaces; work with dangerous machinery, equipment, or tools, or carrying heavy loads; exposure to hazardous substances, agents, or processes, or to temperatures, noise levels, or vibrations that are damaging to health; and work for long hours, night work, and unreasonable confinement to the premises of the employer.

2. INTERNATIONAL LEGAL PRINCIPLES

Several international and regional laws and agreements, as well as United Nations (UN) programs, have talked about the issue of child labor. These laws, agreements, and UN programs were all meant to protect children from economic and social exploitation.

The UN General Assembly of 1959 proclaimed the Declaration of the Rights of the Child to the end that he may have a happy childhood and enjoy, for his own good and for the good of society, the rights and freedoms set forth, and called upon parents, upon men and women as individuals, and upon voluntary organizations, local authorities, and national governments to recognize these rights and strive for their observance by legislative and other measures, progressively taken in accordance with Principle 9 of the Declaration that states the following (University of Minnesota: Human Rights Library, n.d.):

The child shall be protected against all forms of neglect, cruelty, and exploitation. He shall not be the subject of traffic, in any form.

The child shall not be admitted to employment before an appropriate minimum age; he shall in no case be caused or permitted to engage in any occupation or employment that would prejudice his health or education, or interfere with his physical, mental, or moral development.

3. ORGANIZATION FOR ECONOMIC COOPERATION AND DEVELOPMENT CONVENTIONS

The International Labor Organization (ILO) has worked since its inception in 1919 to develop conventions and recommendations that regulate child labor and protect children from all forms of exploitation. This was long before the adoption of the Universal Declaration of the Rights of the Child and the Convention on the Rights of the Child. Some of these agreements specified the minimum age for a child to legally work in certain fields.

The United Nations adopted General Convention No. 138, which established the minimum age, in 1973. To accomplish this goal, it proposed making the legal working age the same as that considered to be an adult in most countries; in most, this age is set at fifteen. Furthermore, it prohibited the employment of minors under the age of 18 "in jobs likely to endanger their health, safety, or morality due to the nature or working conditions." The convention required nations that approved it to develop national policies prohibiting the use of children as laborers.

However, prior to the adoption of Convention No. 138, the ILO had produced several conventions that established the age at which children could no longer be employed in specific occupations (Morcos, 2014). The first of these, Convention No. 5 (1919), established 14 as the minimum age for industry work; this was later raised to 15 by means of Convention (Revised) No. 59 (1937). In 1920, the ILO established 14 as the minimum age for sea employment, by means of Convention No. 7. The minimum age was set at 15 in 1936, by Convention (Revised) No. 58. In 1921, Convention No. 10 established a 14-year-old age limit for agricultural work. Convention No. 15 of 1921 established 18 as the minimum age for trimmers and stokers. In 1932, Convention No. 33, concerning the minimum age in non-industrial employment, set the age at 14; Convention (Revised) No. 60 of 1937, raised the age to 15. The minimum age for fishermen was set at fifteen by means of Convention No. 112 (1959). The minimum age for underground work was set at 16 by means of Convention No. 123 (1965).

Night work by young people under the age of eighteen in industry is prohibited under Convention No. 6 of 1919. In Convention (Revised) No. 90 (1948), regarding the night work of young persons, the modifications did not affect the age requirement that had previously been suggested. Convention No. 79 of 1946 banned night work for young persons under 14 years of age in non-industrial occupations, in order to protect their bodily integrity. Convention No. 16 of 1921 established the compulsory medical examination of young persons (at sea); Convention No. 124 of 1965 established the medical examination of young persons in underground work; Convention No. 77 of 1946 established the medical examination of young persons in industrial work; and Convention No. 78 of 1946 established the medical examination of young persons in non-industrial work. The latter two conventions required medical examinations for anyone under the age of 18 in industrial and non-industrial work unless a medical examination proved that they were fit to carry out such work. They further stipulated that minors under 18 years of age who carry out hazardous work must undergo periodic medical examinations.

In 1998, the ILO came out with a broader statement of basic rights and principles (ILO, 1998). In the second part of the declaration, it was stated that "all Members, even if they have not ratified the Conventions in question, have an obligation, arising from the very fact of membership in the Organization, to respect, to promote, and to realize, in good faith and in accordance with the Constitution, the principles concerning the fundamental rights which are the subject of those Conventions, namely:

- freedom of association and the effective recognition of the right to collective bargaining;
- the elimination of all forms of forced or compulsory labor;
- the effective abolition of child labor;
- the elimination of discrimination in respect of employment and occupation; and
- a safe and healthy working environment.”

As for the practical steps, the International Program for The Elimination of Child Labor (IPEC) was launched in 1992 with the aim of eliminating child labor by supporting the capacities of states and promoting a global anti-child labor movement. This program, carried out in partnership with the International Labour Organization and the World Health Organization, aimed to support and sensitize countries to develop plans and programs to eliminate child labor and keep children away from hazardous work.

4. THE ARAB LABOR AGREEMENTS

The Arab Labour Organization (ALO) includes in its membership all 22 Arab countries (Algeria, Bahrain, Comoros, Djibouti, Egypt, Iraq, Jordan, Kuwait, Lebanon, Libya, Mauritania, Morocco, Oman, Palestine, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, Somalia, Sudan, Syria, Tunisia, the United Arab Emirates, and Yemen) and is the only Arab regional organization with tripartite representation. Founded in 1965, its aims consist of the following (UNESCWA, Arab Labour Organization, n.d.):

- coordinate efforts in the field of labor and workers on the Arab and international levels;
- develop and maintain union rights and freedoms;
- provide technical assistance in the labor domain to the three parties of production in member states;
- improve labor laws in member states and work on unifying them;
- improve the circumstances and conditions of work in member states;
- Develop Arab human resources so that they can reach their full economic and social potential;
- Develop the Arab labor force and enhance its productivity;
- Prepare a manual and lay the foundation for occupational classification and qualification;
- Translate labor and vocational training terminology to Arabic.

Countries in the Arab World have been working hard to eliminate (or reduce) child labor. However, recent unprecedented and tumultuous events, such as armed conflicts, economic shocks, and the COVID-19 pandemic, have presented policymakers with enormous challenges related to child labor. It is estimated that 13.4 million, or 15%, of children in the Arab World, are working. Many experts have raised concerns about the harsh realities of life for these child workers, particularly those in informal sectors such as seasonal agriculture, street labor, and domestic labor, which frequently go unmeasured by authorities. The problem is exacerbated during times of armed conflict and political unrest, when millions of people may be displaced and, as a result, families may resort to child labor to supplement lost earnings. Furthermore, the COVID-19 pandemic, spiraling job losses, and falling incomes have all contributed to the increased prevalence of child labor. The work that children are forced to do is frequently abusive and dangerous, leaving them permanently afflicted, overwhelmed, and distressed; further, it restricts their access to quality education and health care, both of which are regarded as critical pillars for charting a positive future course. Children are forced to work for a variety of reasons. Poverty-stricken families and those without social protection safety nets are particularly vulnerable to economic shocks that affect employment and income. As a result, families are increasingly forcing their children to work in order to survive. This has been evident during several economic crises in

which the countries' progress on reducing child labor and improving school attendance has been reversed (Al-Mulla, 2012; Morcos, 2014; ILO, Child labor in Arab States, n.d.).

4.1 General trends and characteristics

The poorest countries in the Arab World show the highest rates of child employment; this reflects a global trend verified by the latest ILO Global Estimates (ILO, 2017). The general trends of child employment in the region can be summarized as follows (League of Arab States, n.d.):

- child employment increases with age, with higher employment rates in the 15–17 age group than the 5–14 age group. Particular attention should be paid to the fact that 15–17-year-olds do a lot of dangerous work.
- child employment rates are higher among boys. However, it should be noted that surveys might fail to capture hidden forms of child labor among girls, such as domestic work and unpaid household services, which merit further research and inquiry.
- child employment rates are generally higher in rural areas than in urban areas.

The most important things to know about children working in the Arab region are:

- unpaid family work is more common among children ages 5 to 14, girls, and people who live in rural areas. Paid non-family work is more common among children ages 15 to 17, boys, and people who live in cities.
- children aged 15–17, particularly males, tend to work longer hours than their respective counterparts. On the other hand, working children who attend school tend to work less than those who do not go to school.
- children in urban areas tend to work longer hours than rural children. But it should be noted that agricultural work is highly labor-intensive, but seasonal.

4.2 Trends and working conditions by sector

- child labor in the Arab region is mostly found in agriculture, followed by services and industry. Country-level data also point to the following trends:
- children ages 5–14 are more likely to work in agriculture, while 15–17-year-olds are more likely to work in services and industries.
- the sectoral distribution of girls' activities varies a lot from country to country, depending on the nature of the local economy. Keep in mind that household surveys often can't find some of the hidden work that girls do.

4.3 Agriculture: Small-scale farming

The majority of children in the agricultural sector are unpaid family workers, especially children aged 5–14. Child labor in agriculture is mainly related to small-scale farming, where cheap intensive labor is in high demand, especially on family farms that depend on the contribution of children. A closer look at child labor in agriculture in Lebanon, Morocco, Egypt, and Yemen highlights the following push factors: household poverty, low parental education, certain social norms, lack of access to education or lack of enforcement of compulsory education, lack of access to water and electricity networks, and lack of social security.

Agriculture was found to be one of the most hazardous sectors of activity. Children working in this sector are at risk of being exposed to the following hazards, which vary in degree and combination, depending on the activity: exposure to chemicals, pesticides, dust, and smoke; carrying heavy loads; working long hours; repeatedly bending and standing; working at heights; working in isolation; long hours of exposure to the sun and other climatic conditions; and working with dangerous tools and farm machinery, often with a lack of protective gear or access to first aid.

Children working on family farms often lack social and legal protections. Countries can choose to apply certain exemptions allowed under Article 5 of the Minimum Age Convention, 1973 (No. 138), and exclude some children from the legal provisions on the minimum age for work. It should be noted, however, that such exemptions do not apply to any form of hazardous work. In remote rural areas, there are further issues regarding the limited capacity of labor inspectors and the lack of geographical coverage, often leaving rural child labor outside the purview of government oversight.

4.4 Industry and Services: The Informal Sector

Child labor in the secondary and tertiary sectors is generally informal work, which is particularly prone to child labor since, by definition, it escapes regulatory and inspection oversight. In the industrial sector, paid, non-family work is the most common type of child labor. In the services sector, where jobs are more varied, paid, non-family work is the most common type of job.

A closer look at children in informal employment in some Arab countries highlights the following determinants of child labor:

- poverty such that the household relies on the additional income generated by sending children to work, especially among refugees and internally displaced persons (IDPs);
- education is considered of limited value in the absence of future prospects for decent work;
- limited labor inspection capacity; and
- from an employer's perspective, children represent low-cost labor and are easier to manage.

Children working informally face various hazards depending on the type of activity, such as long hours of work, dust and pollution hazards, injury and security risks, carrying heavy loads, and working without protective clothing. Based on the country studies presented here, the majority of children working informally in industry and services do not attend school.

As for young girls (under the age of 16) found in domestic work, they face a disconcerting situation due to the risks of seclusion, the lack of school attendance, and the potential for their rights as children to be violated. In Tunisia, girls were found to be subject to strenuous working conditions and physical abuse from employers. They were also isolated from their families and friends, and poorly paid. The ILO has highlighted the need to improve data collection in order to measure the extent and nature of children's involvement in domestic work across the Arab region, and has called for a strategic policy response to address such child labor.

4.5 Child labor in armed conflict

Children are often the main victims of armed conflicts and population displacement in the region. Child labor is on the rise among refugees and internally displaced populations, as well as among host communities in Lebanon, Jordan, and Iraq. Refugee and displaced children can be found working in a

number of sectors of activity, with a notable rise in street work, bonded labor, early marriage, and commercial sexual exploitation. Child labor among refugee and displaced children is mainly a financial coping mechanism for families who face extreme poverty or where adults are unemployed. Refugee and displaced children also work longer hours for lower pay than local children (Mekay, n.d.).

The UN Secretary-General has reported a rise in the recruitment and use of children by armed groups, among both local and refugee populations. This is certainly the case in Yemen, Syria, and Iraq, where the majority of recruited children are generally boys. However, there is an emerging tendency to recruit more girls, as well as children below the age of 15. Hundreds of children across the Arab region are also held in detention – and even tortured – on the grounds of being involved in armed groups. According to the Secretary-General's report, the factors contributing to such child recruitment are relatively attractive salaries, religious and ideological influences, propaganda, and sometimes pressure and coercion by their communities. Enlistment is not always voluntary, and there is an increasing trend toward forced or deceitful recruitment. Another major concern is the vulnerability of girls to forced marriage, trafficking, and sexual abuse.

Moreover, children living in conflict zones are the greatest victims of the humanitarian crisis. In addition to the extreme conditions of poverty, health and security threats, and the damage to their education, these children are being forced into the kinds of activities associated with armed conflict situations, such as smuggling goods across borders or between fighting zones, collecting oil waste, performing funerary work (collecting body parts for burial), household work, and fetching water or collecting food from fields and landfills, which are even more dangerous in cases of violent conflict.

5. CHILD LABOR IN LEBANON

Action against child labor in Lebanon effectively began in the early 2000s when the Government of Lebanon ratified ILO Conventions No. 182 and No. 138 and signed a Memorandum of Understanding with IPEC as part of a technical cooperation programme agreed upon and implemented in partnership with the ILO Regional Office for the Arab States. This marked the beginning of a series of projects that have been implemented during the last ten years in collaboration with the Ministry of Labor, employers' and workers' organizations, and other national stakeholders. These projects primarily supported the implementation of policy and normative measures accompanied by grassroots activities to combat child labor, with particular attention to its worst forms (Osseiran, 2012; Bureau of International Labor Affairs, 2021).

During the third and final phase of this technical cooperation program (2009–2011), with the financial support of the Italian Government, IPEC reviewed and analyzed national legislation, plans, and strategies related to child labor in Lebanon. This document is the result of this initiative. The overview presented in this study aims to facilitate future efforts to mainstream child labor concerns, especially in the context of national policies and laws. This is vital to sustaining and coordinating efforts to combat child labor using government resources and authority in a manner that is comprehensive, coherent, and sustainable. Moving towards the elimination of child labor in Lebanon requires policy-level dialogue to integrate child labor issues within national development priorities, anti-poverty initiatives, and robust employment generation schemes for adults combined with equal access to quality education (Osseiran, 2012; Bureau of International Labor Affairs, 2021).

In 2021, Lebanon made little progress toward eliminating the most heinous forms of child labor. A UNICEF-funded project trained police officers in Tripoli, Lebanon's northernmost city, to identify child labor and refer children to social services. On the other hand, children in Lebanon are subjected to the worst kinds of child labor, including drug production and trafficking, sometimes as a result of

human trafficking, and forced agricultural labor. Children also work as child laborers in the potato and tobacco industries. Furthermore, government officials have stated time and again that funding is insufficient to carry out their duties. Moreover, labor inspectors can only inspect in formal workplaces, where child labor is almost nonexistent, and social programs aimed at addressing child labor have remained insufficient to fully address the scope of the problem (Bureau of International Labor Affairs, 2021).

Several crises have converged on Lebanon, increasing the rate of child labor, including a national economic crisis that started in 2019 and has since worsened, the continued presence of Syrian refugees, and the COVID-19 pandemic, which has created new barriers to education and accelerated economic decline. The multidimensional poverty rate in Lebanon has risen from 42% in 2019 to 82% in 2021, including nearly all of the country's refugee population. UNICEF reported an increase in child labor from 2.6 percent to 4.4 percent as a result of worsening conditions, with agriculture and street work accounting for the majority of the increase. Furthermore, 12% of families report sending at least one child to work, and Lebanese households have 7 times as many working children as in previous years.

A review of available data on child labor, according to sector and activity, reveals the following (Table 1):

Table 1. Child labor, according to sector and activity

Sector/Industry	Activity
Agriculture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farming, including the production of potatoes, olives, beans, figs, grapes, eggplants, and cannabis. • Production of tobacco. • Fishing, activities unknown.
Industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction, including carpentry, tiling, and welding. • Making handicrafts. • Working in aluminum factories. • Working in slaughterhouses and butcheries.
Services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Street work, including begging, street vending, portering, washing cars, scavenging garbage, and shining shoes. • Maintenance and repair of motor vehicles, and painting. • Domestic work. • Cleaning sewage and collecting waste materials, including scrap metal. • Food service, including working as waiters. • Working in small shops and groceries.
Categorical Worst Forms of Child Labor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Used in illegal activities such as drug production and trafficking, as well as arms dealing. • Forced begging. • Commercial sexual exploitation, sometimes as a result of human trafficking. • Forced labor in agriculture.

5.1 Child labor legislation and regulations

Child labor legislation and regulations have been enacted by the Lebanese government. However, gaps in Lebanon's legal framework exist that prevent children from being subjected to the most heinous forms of child labor, such as the prohibition of commercial sexual exploitation of children. Because they are not performed in industrial, trading, or agricultural enterprises, domestic work and non-

industrial, non-trade agriculture are not covered by the Labor Code. This is contrary to international standards, which require that all children be protected by a minimum working age. In Lebanon, basic education is required. The majority of children complete elementary school by the age of 15. Children may drop out before completing compulsory education because the minimum age for work is lower than the compulsory education age, as shown in Table 2:

Table 2. Child labor legislation and regulations

Standard	Meets International Standards	Age	Legislation
Minimum Age for Work	No	14	Article 22 of the Labor Code
Minimum Age for Hazardous Work	Yes	18	Articles 1-2 and Annex 2 of Decree No. 8987
Identification of Hazardous Occupations or Activities Prohibited for Children	Yes		Annex 1 of Decree No. 8987
Prohibition of Forced Labor	Yes		Article 8 of Decree No. 3855; Articles 569 and 586.1 of the Penal Code
Prohibition of Child Trafficking	Yes		Articles 586.1 and 586.5 of the Penal Code
Prohibition of Commercial Sexual Exploitation of Children	Yes		Articles 506, 523, 525–527, 586.1, and 586.5 of the Penal Code; Decree No. 8987
Prohibition of Using Children in Illicit Activities	Yes		Articles 586.1, 586.5, and 618 of the Penal Code; Article 13 of the Law on Drugs
Minimum Age for Voluntary State Military Recruitment	Yes	18	Article 30 of the National Defense Law
Prohibition of Compulsory Recruitment of Children by (State) Military	N/A*		
Prohibition of Military Recruitment by Non-state Armed Groups	Yes		Article 586.1 of the Penal Code; Annex 1 of Decree No. 8987
Compulsory Education Age	Yes	15	Article 49 of the Education Law
Free Public Education	Yes		Article 49 of the Education Law

Inspections of child labor at informal work sites are permitted only if a complaint is filed and the accused fails to respond to a summons issued by the Child Labor Unit (CLU). There is no mechanism in place to investigate complaints of child domestic labor because social workers—the only officials permitted to enter a private home—can only assess the overall well-being of the family, not the working conditions. According to a limited number of sources, the penalties for violating child labor and other related laws are insufficient to address the issue.

5.2 Agencies Responsible for Child Labor Law Enforcement

The government of Lebanon has set up institutions to make sure that laws and rules against child labor, even in its worst forms, are followed (Table 3).

Table 3. Agencies responsible for child labor law enforcement

Organization/Agency	Role
Ministry of Labor	Enforces child labor laws through desk reviews and workplace inspections. The Ministry's Child Labor Unit acts as the government's focal point for child labor issues and raises public awareness about child labor and the right to education. Receives complaints of child labor violations on its Child Labor Unit hotline.
Internal Security Forces (ISF)	Enforces laws regarding child labor through the Anti-Human Trafficking and Moral Crimes Unit.
Ministry of Justice	Prosecutes violations of the Penal Code in coordination with the ISF. Maintains general data and statistics on criminal violations involving child labor. Refers at-risk children to shelters and protection services. Coordinates, through signed agreements, with civil society organizations to provide social workers who oversee court proceedings involving juveniles and deliver services to them, including children engaged in begging.
Directorate of General Security	Focuses on immigration and border protection. Works with the farmers' union to address child labor in agriculture.

5.3 Coordination of Government Efforts on Child Labor

Lebanon's government has put in place mechanisms to coordinate its efforts to combat child labor, including its most heinous forms (Table 4).

Table 4. Coordination of government efforts on child labor

Coordinating Body	Role & Description
National Steering Committee on Child Labor	Raises awareness; coordinates efforts among government agencies; establishes standard practices; develops, enforces, and recommends changes; and ensures that government agencies comply with the law. Led by the Minister of Labor, the delegation includes representatives from six other ministries, other institutions, and international organizations.
National Steering Committee on Trafficking in Persons	Coordinates efforts against human trafficking, including child trafficking. It is based at the Ministry of Labor and meets on a monthly basis.
UNICEF and UNHCR	Coordinate efforts to address the needs of children affected by the Syrian refugee crisis in Lebanon. UN representatives identify crucial concerns, including factors that make children vulnerable to child labor. Make recommendations to the government on the use of resources, including referral services. UN agencies and international and local NGOs coordinate child protection efforts through Child Protection Working Groups.

5.4 Government policies on child labor

The government has enacted policies concerning child labor (Table 5). However, policy gaps, including a lack of implementation, impede efforts to address child labor.

Table 5. Policies related to child labor

Policy	Description
National Action Plan on the Elimination of the Worst Forms of Child Labor (2013–2016)	Establishes strategies for addressing the worst forms of child labor. Includes a National Awareness Strategy to be carried out by the ILO. Full funding for the \$23 million implementation budget has not been secured.
National Social Development Strategy	Establishes a plan for a comprehensive social, health, and educational program. Includes the protection of working children and the implementation of HCC's strategy to address the needs of street children.
Ministry of Economy's (MOEs) Education Sector Development Plan	Aims to improve retention and educational achievement in areas with high dropout rates. Funded by the EU.
Ministry of Social Affairs' (MOSA's) Higher Council for Childhood (HCC)	Implements children's rights policies, including combating child labor.

5.5 Social Programs to Address Child Labor

In 2013, the government of Lebanon paid for and took part in programs that aimed to end or stop even the worst kinds of child labor (Table 6).

Table 6. Social programs to address child labor

Program	Description
Child Protection Program	Joint program by UNICEF and the Ministry of Social Affairs. Addresses child labor through interventions, including a non-formal education program for children, child protection services, skills development, and social assistance.
Reaching All Children	A donor-funded, 5-year project, implemented by the Ministry of Education and Higher Education and partners, aims to ensure quality educational opportunities for children ages 3 to 18, regardless of nationality, through holistic interventions that address the demand for and availability of quality public education, including non-formal education.
National Poverty Alleviation Program	Funded by the government and foreign donors, this program, housed at the Prime Minister's Office and Ministry of Social Affairs, provided WFP food vouchers (\$27 per month) for each member of poor families. It also provided school tuition and book costs for secondary school students from 43,000 poor families.

Although Lebanon has programs to address child labor, the scope of these programs is insufficient to fully address the extent of the problem, including forced child labor in agriculture. Furthermore, due to a lack of adequate social services, some officials are hesitant to remove children trafficked by their families.

The prevalence of the phenomenon of child labor is not related to the insufficiency of texts, in terms of international agreements and legislative texts in this area, but the problem is mainly related to the lack of internal policies aimed at enshrining these rights and developing appropriate plans for their enforcement, as well as the effectiveness of the application, where the incubating environment of this phenomenon must be eliminated through a well-developed plan and an effective socio-economic policy strategy. It should be noted that Lebanon has played a positive role in this regard through its determination to put an end to this scourge by harmonizing its legislation with international agreements

and the practical steps that it has taken and continues to take toward strengthening the fight against child labor. A good step, but not enough in the absence of a well-defined plan.

6. CONCLUSION

Sustainable and systematic solutions must be at the heart of child labor strategies. Central governments must invest in data systems that track child labor rates across different age groups, income levels, and geographies, as well as the types of work they do, to better understand regional vulnerabilities and the root causes that exacerbate the trend. The implementation of comprehensive birth registration systems that aid in the tracking of children is deemed necessary. Policymakers should constantly develop job-creation policies to assist in providing fair and adequate opportunities for families to break the cycle of poverty. Authorities should also conduct regular workplace inspections to identify instances of child labor. At the same time, solid social protection schemes for families, such as housing assistance, school tuition, healthcare services, and childcare, as well as cash payments, are needed to offset the need to rely on child labor to improve livelihoods.

Parenting education programs can help people learn about the dangers of child labor and question social norms that may support it unintentionally. Child labor should be identified and reported by community advocates as well. In tandem, national legislation must be enacted to protect children's fundamental rights to education, healthcare, well-being, and safety. Suggested actions to advance the elimination of child labor in the Arab World in general and Lebanon in particular are presented below (Table 7).

Table 7. Suggested actions to eliminate child labor

Area	Suggested Action
Legal Framework	Raise the minimum age for work to the age at which education is compulsory.
	Make sure that the minimum age to work applies to all children, including those who work informally, in homes, or on farms.
Enforcement	Make sure there is a good way to receive complaints about child labor, write them down, and send them to an investigation.
	Track and publish information on labor law enforcement.
	Authorize the labor inspectorate to assess penalties.
	Provide the Ministry of Labor's inspectors with proper funding and resources.
	Increase the number of labor inspectors to meet the ILO's technical advice.
	Publish information on the criminal enforcement of child labor laws.
Government Policies	Make sure that criminal law enforcement agencies, like the Internal Security Forces' anti-human trafficking unit, have the money and people they need to investigate and prosecute cases of child labor that break the law.
	Ensure that the Work Plan to Prevent and Respond to the Association of Children with Armed Violence in Lebanon is implemented, and that children previously associated with armed conflict receive social and rehabilitation services.
	Make sure that key policies about child labor are put into action during the reporting period and that information about these activities is made public.
Social Programs	Adopt a new action plan to address the worst forms of child labor.
	Collect and share information about how much and what kind of child labor there is so that policies and programs can be made.
	Make sure that all children, including refugees, can go to public school by improving transportation, dealing with bullying and harassment, taking care of students with disabilities, and improving facilities.
	Expand programs, such as those that offer social services to people who have been victims of human trafficking, to deal with the full extent of child labor, including forced labor in agriculture and construction.

Noteworthy is that more than half of the 22 Arab countries, with a population of 420 million people, are currently affected by conflicts or inflows of refugees and internally displaced persons. These include: Iraq, Jordan, Lebanon, Libya, Somalia, Sudan, Syria, Tunisia, Egypt, and Yemen. As is the case across the globe, conflict has hit women and children disproportionately hard in the region. In consequence, child labor has emerged as perhaps the most critical child-protection issue in the region, requiring our urgent attention and action. The effects of recent economic shocks, political turmoil, conflict, and war have worsened pre-existing levels of child labor and also reversed much of the progress Arab countries had made in combating child labor through policy development and practical measures. On the other hand, Arab governments have generally worked to combat child labor through legislation but have often failed to rein in abuse because of the spread of corruption, a lack of oversight, and their own contribution to political instability. Some countries have even restricted the work of some NGOs whose activities include combating child labor (Mekay, n.d.).

The International Rescue Committee's project in Lebanon, which the EU's Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid funded, came to the following conclusions (IRC and LPC, 2021):

- An increased use of child labor as a negative coping mechanism is due to food insecurity and deteriorating nutrition practices. The inability to provide food is one of the main triggers for parents to send their children to work, and the primary use of children's income is for food.
- Children are increasingly reporting becoming the main breadwinners for their families. However, even when they are working, the children and their families suffer acutely from food insecurity and resort to food-based coping mechanisms; 84% of the working children surveyed have been worried that their household would not have enough to eat, and 56% of the working children surveyed reported going to bed hungry.
- Food insecure working children are more likely to face short- and long-term consequences: 50% of the surveyed children had wounds. Children report suffering from tiredness (24% of the communities surveyed by LPC), body pain (19%), exposure to verbal and physical abuse (13%), and psychological distress (12%). The children are very likely to have some form of micronutrient deficiency and stunted growth. Their well-being and mental health are dramatically impacted. There is a concern over the possible increased risk of child marriage.

It is clear from the above that there is a strong correlation between child labor and food insecurity; the inability to provide food is one of the main triggers for parents to send their children to work, and the primary use of children's income is for food; children in Lebanon are increasingly reporting becoming the main breadwinners for their families. Since 2019, Lebanon has been dealing with an unprecedented number of crises that have brought the country to its knees. The country's resources, health system, and businesses have been strained as a result of the financial and socioeconomic crisis, as well as COVID-19 and the Beirut Blast of 2020. Over half of Lebanon's population lives in poverty (World Bank, 2020), and 9 out of 10 refugees (UNHCR, 2020) live in extreme poverty. Unemployment has risen in the last couple of years (Commerce du Levant, 2020; UNOCHA, 2020), affecting both Lebanese and Syrian workers. Thus, it is of utmost importance to mainstream child labor efforts into inter-sector priorities and programming. Also, there is an immediate need for food security and basic assistance programs for working children and their families that include nutrition and case management. There is also a need for programs that deal with child labor over a longer period of time and that combine food security and nutrition.

Millions of people in Lebanon have been forced into poverty and have reduced their food consumption. Three years into the economic crisis, the government has not acted adequately, and the existing system reaches a tiny share of those with low incomes, leaving the majority completely unprotected. Rising unemployment, a weakening local currency, skyrocketing inflation, and the elimination of medicine and fuel subsidies have made it difficult for many people to meet their basic needs. Nearly four out of every five households had a wage earner who had lost their job since the crisis began in 2019, with about 15% still unemployed. Households with an unemployed member were more likely to struggle to make ends meet (Human Rights Watch, 2022). Existing social assistance programs, which are partially funded by the World Bank, have limited coverage and target households in extreme poverty, leaving large segments of the population vulnerable to hunger, unable to obtain medicines, and subject to other deprivations that undermine their rights, such as the right to food and health. The government has not yet come up with a national plan for social security that protects everyone's right to it.

According to Human Rights Watch (2022), the severity of the current economic crisis highlights the urgent need for a universal, rights-based social protection system that leaves no one behind, fulfilling everyone's right to an adequate standard of living and to social security that fulfills this right. Donors and governments should recognize widespread suffering and devise a system to provide basic social security guarantees, such as child, disability, and unemployment benefits, as well as old-age pensions, in which the state is responsible for ensuring that everyone has access to food and income security. Both the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) and the International Covenant on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights recognize the right to social security. Article 25 of the UN's Universal Declaration of Human Rights says, "Everyone has the right to a standard of living adequate for the health and well-being of himself and his family, including food, clothing, housing, medical care, and necessary social services, and the right to security in the event of unemployment, sickness, disability, widowhood, old age, or other circumstances that leave him without a way to make a living."

Lebanon's population is approximately 6.7 million people. The United Nations estimated in late 2021 that nearly half of Lebanon's population, or 3.28 million people, had fallen into poverty since the country's economic crisis began in 2019 (Human Rights Watch, 2022). Others who were already struggling to fulfill their basic economic rights, such as food, education, or health care, saw their situation deteriorate. More adults skipped meals or were unable to afford medicines, and more children were forced to work to support their families. To make matters worse, the ongoing conflict in Ukraine has increased the cost of staple foods and energy.

For years, the political establishment was aware of the impending disaster, but did little to prevent it. A legal vacuum allowed capital to flow out of the country, allowing well-connected individuals to move their money out of the country. As a matter of human rights, truth and accountability must be sought. Political leaders in Lebanon are completely disconnected from reality, including the desperation they have created by destroying people's lives. Lebanon is also one of the most unequal countries in the world, and the country's leadership appears to be unaware of this at best, and complicit in it at worst.

In conclusion, if hope for a better future is to be restored in Lebanon, future governments must strengthen the Central Inspection, remove potential political interference from the National Anti-Corruption Commission, and incorporate accountability and transparency into recovery plans. The governments must also commit to improving human rights records in all areas, including reducing inequality, combating corruption and impunity, constructing strong and resilient social protection, education and healthcare systems, and prioritizing public interests over private profits. By any means, the destructive actions of Lebanon's political and financial leaders are to blame for most of the country's people living in poverty, which is against international human rights law.

REFERENCES

- Al-Mulla, S. (2022, June 12). *Ending child labor in the region must be a priority*. Arab News. Available from: <https://www.arabnews.com/node/2101941>
- Bureau of International Labor Affairs - U.S. Department of Labor (2021). *Findings on the Worst Forms of Child Labor: Lebanon*. Available from: https://www.dol.gov/sites/dolgov/files/ILAB/child_labor_reports/tda2020/Lebanon.pdf
- Commerce du Levant (July 2020). *Le taux de chômage au Liban a triplé depuis début 2019, selon Infopro*. <https://www.lecommercedulevant.com/article/29889-le-taux-de-chomage-au-liban-a-triple-depuis-debut-2019-seloninfopro>
- ESCWA - Arab Labour Organization (n.d.). Cairo, Egypt. Available from: <https://www.unescwa.org/sd-glossary/arab-labour-organization-alo>
- Human Rights Watch (2022, December 12). *Lebanon: Rising Poverty, Hunger Amid Economic Crisis - Government and World Bank Should Invest in Rights-Based Social Protection*. Available from: <https://www.hrw.org/news/2022/12/12/lebanon-rising-poverty-hunger-amid-economic-crisis>
- ILO (2017). *Global Estimates of Child Labour: Results and Trends, 2012-2016*. International Labour Office, Geneva, Switzerland. Available from: https://www.ilo.org/global/publications/books/WCMS_575499/lang-en/index.htm
- ILO (2015). *World report on child labour 2015: Paving the way to decent work for young people*. International Labour Office, Geneva: Switzerland. Available from: https://www.ilo.org/ipecc/Informationresources/WCMS_358969/lang-en/index.htm
- ILO (1998). *ILO Declaration on Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work*. International Labour Office, Geneva, Switzerland. Retrieved from: <https://www.ilo.org/declaration/thedeclaration/textdeclaration/lang-en/index.htm>
- ILO (n.d.). *Conventions on child labour*. International Labour Office, Geneva, Switzerland. Available from: <https://www.ilo.org/ipecc/facts/ILOconventionsonchildlabour/lang-en/index.htm>
- ILO (n.d.). *Hazardous child labour: What is hazardous child labour or hazardous work?* International Labour Office, Geneva, Switzerland. Available from: <https://www.ilo.org/ipecc/facts/WorstFormsofChildLabour/Hazardouschildlabour/lang-en/index.htm>
- ILO (n.d.). *Child labour in Arab States*. International Labour Office, Geneva, Switzerland. Available from: <https://www.ilo.org/ipecc/Regionsandcountries/arab-states/lang-en/index.htm>
- International Rescue Committee (IRC) and the Lebanon Protection Consortium (LPC) - which includes Action Against Hunger (ACF), Gruppo di Volontariato Civile (GVC) and the Norwegian Refugee Council (NRC) (2021, February). *Working children in crisis-hit Lebanon: exploring the linkages between food insecurity and child labour*.
- League of Arab States, International Labour Organization, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, Arab Labour Organization and Arab Council for Childhood and Development (2019). *Child labour in the arab region a quantitative and qualitative analysis*. Available from: https://www.ilo.org/beirut/publications/WCMS_675262/lang-en/index.htm
- Mekay, E. (n.d.). *Middle East: Child labour on the rise as conflicts and tensions grow*. International Bar Association, London, UK. Available from: <https://www.ibanet.org/article/6EE5DBD3-FEEF-4400-B4FC-B1CC9F4ECBE6>
- Morcos, P. (2014, January). *Child labour: international law and Lebanese legislation*. Human & Health magazine. Syndicate of Hospitals in Lebanon, No. 26, pp. 20-24. Available from: https://www.syndicateofhospitals.org.lb/Content/uploads/SyndicateMagazinePdfs/5006_20-25ar.pdf

Osseiran, H. (2012). *Action against child labour in Lebanon A mapping of policy and normative initiatives*. International Labour Office, Geneva, Switzerland. Available from: https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---arabstates/---ro-beirut/documents/genericdocument/wcms_210577.pdf

University of Minnesota: Human Rights Library (n.d.). Available from: <http://hrlibrary.umn.edu/instree/k1drc.htm#:~:text=Principle%209&text=The%20child%20shall%20not%20be,physical%2C%20mental%20or%20moral%20development>.

UNDP (2015). *Human Development Report 2015*. Available from: <https://www.undp.org/publications/human-development-report-2015> Work for Human Development.

United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR), United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), World Food Program (WFP), and Inter-Agency Coordination (2020). *Vulnerability Assessment of Syrian Refugee in Lebanon (VASyR)*

United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (UNOCHA) (August 2020): *Lebanon Flash Appeal*.

World Bank (WB) (October 2020). *Lebanon Economic Update*. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/lebanon/publication/economic-update-october-2020>

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